

ESTIMATION OF MECHANICAL BEHAVIORS FOR TEXTILE COMPOSITES BASED ON MULTI-SCALE ANALYSIS

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1 Introduction

3D Textile composites have been studied for many years in replacement of laminate structures in composite materials. Especially, a stitched textile composite and woven composites are remarkable materials because they have some advantages.

In the case of NCF, the stitching yarn brings the enhancement of strength in out-of-plane direction, and the improvement in formability, lower rate of crimp are the advantages. Recently, several works have been reported in the literatures regarding FE-based model of NCF composites. Tserpes et al. reported a meso-mechanical approach of NCF composite structural parts based on RVE (representative volume elements) and homogenized progressive failure analysis [1]. Himmel et al. developed a FE based unit-cell model considering the thickness and fiber orientation of the layers and the shape and size of resin pockets [2]. Mikhaluk et al. reported a multi-scale FE homogenization to obtain effective mechanical properties of NCF composites with account of resin-rich zones and various fiber volume fraction values [3].

Woven fabric composites have been also used in many industrial applications because they have advantages such as easy handling and high lateral strength. The previous research about mechanical characterization of woven fabric composites established theoretical and experimental investigations, which were based on mechanical behavior at macro scale which means "composite part scale" [4-6]. In order to evaluate fiber cracking, resin failure, delamination which relate to meso and micro scale structures, the recent studies have tried to generate more detailed FE models based on meso scale which means "fiber geometric scale" and micro scale which means "filament scale" [7].

However, Non Crimped Fabric (NCF) and woven composites have many design parameters such as volume fraction of fiber, architecture of reinforced fibers, matrix properties, etc. Furthermore, it is very difficult to evaluate the mechanical behaviors because of the complicated geometrical shape.

For an evaluation of mechanical property of textile composites with several parameters, FEM is one of effective methods in order to reduce the development times and the costs. Therefore, the purpose of this study is to establish an estimation procedure of mechanical characterization for NCF composites and off-axis woven laminates based on multi-scale analysis.

In this study, the mesh superposition method, which is one of the multi-scale analytical methods of FEM, is applied. Two types of numerical models composed of a global model and local model have been generated. The advantages of the mesh superposition method are that interaction between the matrix and the fabric and that the mechanical behaviors of each mesh can be estimated by one operation. The mechanical behavior for woven composites and NCF composites under static loading has been estimated based on the multi-scale analytical method.

2 FE Modeling and Numerical Results for NCF

2.1 Numerical modeling

In order to estimate the mechanical behavior of NCF composites, the geometrical model and FE model had been generated as follows;

The geometrical data of NCF is generated by WiseTex software in Fig.1, which has been developed by Lomov et. al [8]. FE modeling of NCF is implemented by MeshTex in Fig.2, which is the FE modeling software for fiber reinforced composites developed by Zako, etc [9]. Since

geometry of NCF is complex, it is not easy to generate FE models integrally. Therefore, stitching yarn part and laminates part are modeled individually. In order to consider the interaction of each part, the mesh superposition method is applied to the FE analysis in Fig.3.

Fig.1 Geometrical model by WiseTEX

Fig.2 FE model by MeshTEX

Fig.3 Numerical modeling of mesh superposition method for NCF composites

2.2 Mesh Superposition Method

In the Mesh superposition method, stitching yarn is defined as local mesh, and laminate model is treated as the global mesh. Analytical area is divided into global area ($\Omega^G = \Omega \setminus \Omega^L$) and local area (Ω^L) as shown in Fig.4. Ω^G is the area where only global mesh exists, and Ω^L is the area determined both global mesh and local mesh. The boundary between two meshes is defined as Γ^{GL} , and surface forces affect not Γ^{GL} but only the external boundary (Γ^S), because Ω^L is perfectly inside Ω^G . On those assumptions, the stiffness equation is represented as shown in Eq.(1).

This method has some advantages. The local-mesh can be superimposed on a macro-mesh without considering the matching of boundary for each mesh.

Fig.4 Mesh superposition method

$$\begin{bmatrix} [K^G] & [K^{GL}] \\ [K^{LG}] & [K^L] \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \{d^G\} \\ \{d^L\} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} \{F^S\} \\ \{0\} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

Each argument in Eq.(1) is indicated with the following equations.

$$\left. \begin{aligned} [K^G] &= \int_{\Omega^G} [B^G]^T [D^G] [B^G] d\Omega \\ &\quad + \int_{\Omega^L} [B^G]^T [D^L] [B^G] d\Omega \\ [K^L] &= \int_{\Omega^L} [B^L]^T [D^L] [B^L] d\Omega \\ [K^{GL}] &= \int_{\Omega^L} [B^G]^T [D^L] [B^L] d\Omega \\ [K^{LG}] &= \int_{\Omega^L} [B^L]^T [D^L] [B^G] d\Omega = [K^{GL}]^T \\ [F^S] &= \int_{\Gamma^S} [N^G]^T \{t\} d\Gamma. \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (2)$$

Where, [N] and {d} have been shape function matrix and displacement respectively, and suffix G and L have represented the domain of global and local. [B]

is strain-displacement matrix, and $[D]$ is stress-strain matrix.

2.3 Numerical Model of NCF

The test specimen has been prepared as glass fiber / polyester composites. Figure 5 shows the stitching pattern and geometry of a specimen for NCF composites. The stitching pattern is a promat type, and the laminate consisted of four plies. Two layers are stitched and laminated to each other symmetrically. The data of fiber, resin, and volume fraction are shown in Table 1.

Fig.5 Geometry of NCF specimen

Table 1 Data of fiber and resin

Reinforced fiber	E-glass	
Resin	Polyester resin	
Stitching yarn	Polyester yarn	
Volume fraction	[90]	51.7 %
	[0]	51.2 %
Width of opening resin region	[90]	0.70 mm
	[0]	0.39 mm
Thickness of layer	[90]	0.65 mm
	[0]	0.68 mm

(a) Global FE model (b) Local FE model
Fig.6 Numerical model of NCF composites

To estimate the damage development of NCF composites, FE models for NCF composites have been prepared as shown in Fig.6. The model has the structure with considering the resin-rich zones, and

the geometry of the resin-rich zone is obtained from the surface observation of the testing specimens. In the simulation, the modeling of damage is very important. NCF composites are treated as heterogeneous bodies with anisotropy for fiber bundles and with isotropy for matrix, respectively. The isotropic damage model is applied for matrix, and anisotropic damage model is applied for the fiber bundle, respectively [10]. The occurrence of damage can be predicted by Hoffman's criterion.

2.4 Numerical Results

Mechanical behaviors under static bending load are estimated with the mesh superposition method. Figure 7 shows the stress distribution in X-direction on [0] ply at tension side. As the comparison of this numerical result, the mechanical behaviors are also estimated without mesh superposition method. As the results, in the case of mesh superposition method, the stress concentration caused by the stitching yarn can be estimated. It is implied that the stress concentration induces the reduction of in-plane deformation of NCF composites.

(a) With mesh superposition method (Laminate with stitch)

(b) Without mesh superposition method (Laminate part)

Fig.7 Stress distribution in [0] ply ($\epsilon = 1.05\%$)

Figure 8 shows the numerical results of damage state. The initial damage appears in [90] ply as transverse cracks. The purple color means the damaged elements judged by the Hoffman's criterion.

As the comparison, Figure 9 shows the observational results of damage development in static bending test. The damages developed in the central region between opening resin region. From these results, the tendency of damage development is almost same with the experimental and numerical results.

Figure 10 shows the numerical results of stiffness - strain curve. There are same tendency of the stiffness reduction. From these results, the effect of stitching yarn on the mechanical behavior of NCF composites can be estimated by the proposed multi-scale analysis.

Fig.8 Damage state in [90] ply ($\epsilon = 1.49\%$)

Fig.9 Experimental results of damage state

Fig.10 Stiffness reduction

3 FE Modeling and Numerical Results for Off-axis Woven Composites

3.1 Numerical modeling

By using the WiseTex and MeshTex program, the modeling of woven part and the resin part are separated. And, the mesh superposition method is applied in order to consider the interaction of each model in Fig.11.

Fig.11 Numerical modeling of mesh superposition method for off-axis woven composites

Figure 12 shows the procedure of the modeling of woven angle-ply.

Firstly, a unit model of woven structure is generated by using WiseTEX and MeshTEX. In order to apply the angle-ply, the unit model is rotated like this. And, the rotated model is divided into the small region in order to consider the boundary of angle-ply laminate. And, in the divided region, we estimate the geometry between fiber bundle and resin, and classify the several geometries. We carry out the mesh generation of 2D and 3D mesh for fiber bundles.

Finally, the all meshes with several geometries are connected, and we can get the finite element mesh of

woven angle-ply laminate. The mesh is superimposed on the resin mesh, and the periodic boundary condition is applied to the global model.

Fig.12 Procedure of modeling of woven angle-ply

3.2 Numerical results of woven angle-ply composites

Figure 13 shows the numerical results of woven angle-ply laminates under static tensile loading. In order to make clear the stress distribution state inside the strand, the only strand parts are illustrated. The figure shows the distribution of in-plane shear stress of woven angle-ply laminates. It is recognized that the difference of stress distribution caused by

the fiber orientation of the outer layer can be estimated with the proposed method.

(a)[(-15/75)/(0/90)/(-15/75)]

(b)[(-45/45)/(0/90)/(-45/45)]

Fig.13 Distribution of shear stress (τ_{xy})

(a)[(-15/75)/(0/90)/(-15/75)]

(b)[(-45/45)/(0/90)/(-45/45)]

Fig.14 Distribution of strain in out-of-direction (ϵ_z)

Figure 14 show the strain distribution in out-of-plane direction for the global model. From these results, the strain distribution is quite different due to the angle-ply layer. The effects of woven angle-ply on initial damage can be estimated with the proposed method.

4 Conclusions

For evaluation of mechanical properties of NCF composites and Off-axis woven composites, FE modeling system for textile composites has been developed. In the system, the geometrical data are determined by WiseTex, and FE models are generated by MeshTex. And, the mesh superposition method is applied to FE analysis. In the case of NCF, FE meshes of stitching yarn and laminates with resin-rich region are modeled individually. In the case of woven angle-ply, the FE meshes of woven part and the resin part are also separated.

From the numerical results, the mechanical behaviors of NCF and Off-axis woven composites can be estimated. In the case of NCF, the stiffness reduction under static bending has same tendency with the numerical and experimental results.

In the case of woven angle-ply, effects of woven angle-ply on stress and strain distributions can be also estimated conveniently with the proposed method.

It is recognized that the proposed mesh superposition method is very convenient for the estimation of mechanical behaviors of NCF composites and off-axis woven laminates.

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